

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF BUCCAL TABLETS OF POORLY SOLUBLE DRUG ZALEPLON

*¹Shwetha G. L., ²Mr. Subhan Sab

*¹M. Pharm, ²Assistant Professor,

Department of Pharmaceutics, SJM College of Pharmacy, Chitradurga – 577502.

Article Received on 14 October 2025,
Article Revised on 04 Nov. 2025,
Article Published on 16 Nov. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17614798>

*Corresponding Author

Shwetha G. L.

M. Pharm, Department of
Pharmaceutics, SJM college of
Pharmacy, Chitradurga – 577502.

How to cite this Article: *¹Shwetha G. L.,
²Mr. Subhan Sab. (2025) FORMULATION
AND EVALUATION OF BUCCAL TABLETS
OF POORLY SOLUBLE DRUG ZALEPLON.
"World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research,
14(22), 791-824.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons
Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

In the present investigation, an attempt was made to formulate mucoadhesive buccal tablets containing Zaleplon for the treatment of insomnia. The tablets were prepared by direct compression method using sodium CMC, crospovidone, and other excipients. The buccal route was selected to enhance bioavailability, absorption and patient compliance while bypassing first-pass metabolism and providing a faster onset of action. The formulation was optimized using Central Composite Design by selecting sodium CMC and crospovidone as independent variables and mucoadhesive strength and % drug release as dependent variables. Various formulations were prepared by altering polymer and superdisintegrant concentrations along with binder, lubricant, glidant and diluent. The powder blend was evaluated for pre-compression parameters and the compressed tablets were tested for post-

compression parameters such as weight variation, thickness, hardness, friability, drug content, swelling index, mucoadhesive strength and *In-vitro* drug release. The optimized formulation (OPT-F) showed a mucoadhesive strength of 13.62 g and 93.15% drug release within 30 minutes. The results of the evaluation tests obtained were within Pharmacopoeial limits. Stability studies indicated no significant change in physical or chemical parameters. Hence, Zaleplon buccal tablets were successfully developed for immediate release with enhanced bioavailability and improved patient compliance.

KEYWORDS: Zaleplon, Beta-cyclodextrin, Sodium CMC, Crospovidone, Direct

compression, Buccal tablets.

INTRODUCTION

A novel drug delivery system is one where the man searches for a new method of drug entry into the body in order to show its activity in the body. For many decades, treatment of an acute disease or a chronic illness has been mostly accomplished by delivering drugs using various pharmaceutical dosage forms, including tablets, capsules, pills, suppositories, creams, ointments, liquids, aerosols and injectable carriers. New drug delivery systems have been developed are mucoadhesive drug delivery systems, drug patches, transdermal patches etc.^[1] In recent years interest in novel routes of drug administration has arisen from their ability to enhance the bioavailability of drugs. Drug delivery via the buccal route using bio-adhesive dosage forms offers such a novel route of drug administration. Buccal delivery involves the administration of the desired drug through the buccal mucosal membrane lining of the oral cavity.^[2]

The mucosal lining of the oral cavity offers some advantages. It is richly vascularized and more accessible for the administration and removal of a dosage form. Additionally, buccal drug delivery has highly patient acceptability compared to other non-oral routes of drug administration. Drug absorption through the buccal mucosa is mainly achieved by passive diffusion into the lipoidal membrane. After absorption, the drug is transported through the facial vein, which drains into the general circulation via the jugular vein, passing the liver and thereby sparing the drug from first-pass metabolism.^[3]

Overview of Oral Mucosa^[4,5]

Fig. 01: Anatomy of the oral mucosa.

The oral mucosa is composed of an outermost layer of stratified squamous epithelium. Below this lies a basement membrane, a lamina propria followed by the submucosa as the innermost layer. The epithelium serves as a mechanical barrier protecting the underlying tissues whereas the lamina propria acts as a mechanical support and carries blood vessels and nerves. The stratified squamous epithelium has a mitotically active basal layer and produces different cell layers, where cells are shed from the surface of the epithelium. The epithelium of the buccal mucosa is about 40-50 cell layers thick. The epithelial cells increase in size and become flatter as they travel from the basal layers to the superficial layers.

The oral mucosal thickness varies depending on the site of the buccal mucosa measures at 500-800 μm , while the mucosal thickness of the hard and soft palates, the floor of the mouth, the ventral tongue and the gingivae measure at about 100-200 μm . The composition of the epithelium also varies depending on the site in the oral cavity.

The gingivae and hard palate are keratinized similar to the epidermis. The mucosa of the soft palate, the sublingual and the buccal regions are non keratinized. The keratinized epithelia contain neutral lipids like ceramides and acyl ceramides which have been associated with the barrier function. These epithelia are relatively impermeable to water. In contrast, non keratinized epithelia do not contain acyl ceramides but only have small amount of ceramide. They also contain small amount of polar lipids mainly cholesterol sulfate and glucosyl ceramides. These epithelia have been found to be more permeable to water than keratinized epithelia.

Saliva is the protective fluid for all tissues of the oral cavity. It protects the soft tissues from abrasion by rough materials and from chemicals. It allows for the continuous mineralization of the tooth enamel after eruption and helps in remineralization of the enamel in the early stages of dental caries. Saliva is an aqueous fluid with 1% organic and inorganic materials. The major determinant of the salivary composition is the flow rate which in turn depends upon three factors like the time of day, the type of stimulus and the degree of stimulation. The salivary pH ranges from 5.5 to 7 depending on the flow rate. At high flow rate the Sodium and Bicarbonate concentration increases by increase in pH. The daily salivary volume is between 0.5 to 2 liters and available to hydrate oral mucosal dosage forms.

Absorption via buccal mucosa^[6]

There are two permeation pathways for passive drug transport across the oral mucosa i.e.

paracellular and transcellular routes. Permeants can use these two routes simultaneously but one route is usually preferred over the other depending on the physicochemical properties of the diffusant. Since the intercellular spaces and cytoplasm are hydrophilic in character and lipophilic compounds would have low solubility in this environment. The cell membrane is lipophilic in nature and hydrophilic solutes will have difficulty in permeating through the cell membrane due to a low partition coefficient. Therefore, the intercellular spaces act as the major barrier for permeation of lipophilic compounds and the cell membrane acts as the major transport barrier for hydrophilic compounds. Since the oral epithelium is stratified, solute permeation may involve a combination of these two routes. The route that predominates is generally the one that provides the least amount of hindrance to passage.

Why Buccal Mucosa?^[7]

The oral mucosa is highly perfused with blood vessels at a high blood flow rate of 20- 30 mL/min for each 100gm of the tissue. The blood vessels which are close to the surface and the lymphatic drainage are also well developed. Hence therapeutic concentration of the drug can be achieved rapidly.

Mucoadhesion/Bioadhesion^[8]

‘Bioadhesive’ is defined as a substance that is capable of interacting with biological material and being retained on them or holding them together for extended period of time. Bioadhesive are classified into three types.

- Bioadhesion between biological layers without involvement of artificial materials. Cell diffusion and cell aggregation are good examples.
- Bioadhesion can be represented by cell adhesion into culture dishes or adhesion to a variety of substances including metals, woods and other synthetic materials.
- Adhesion of artificial substances to biological substrate such as adhesion of polymer to skin or other soft tissue.

Factors Important for Mucoadhesion^[9]

1. Polymer Related Factors

- a. Molecular weight
- b. Concentration of Active Polymers
- c. Flexibility of Polymer Chains
- d. Spatial Conformation

2. Environment Related Factors

- a. Applied Strength
- b. pH
- c. Initial Contact Time
- d. Swelling

3. Physiological Variables

- a. Mucin Turnover
- b. Disease States

Mechanism Of Mucoadhesion^[10]

There are two phases involved in the mechanism of mucoadhesion.

1. The contact stage
2. The consolidation stage

Fig. 02: Two steps of mucoadhesion.

- Step 1: The contact stage is the first point of interaction between the drug's two surface polymers and the mucus surface. Following the polymer's soaking and swelling, these two surfaces physically combine.
- Step 2: The stage of consolidation involves the bioadhesive polymer's interpenetration into the mucous membrane. The primary mechanism of attachment is the entanglement of the adhesive chemicals with the extended mucus chain which is followed by the non-covalent interaction induced creation of secondary bonds.

Mucoadhesion Theories^[11]

The various theories have been studied on the basis of physiochemical properties of bioadhesive material and polymer-polymer interaction. Although basis of mucoadhesion is still not understood.

1. Electronic theory
2. Adsorption theory
3. Wetting theory
4. Diffusion theory
5. Fracture theory
6. Mechanical theory

Buccal Drug Delivery System^[12]

Buccal delivery of drugs provides an attractive and alternative route to the oral route of drug administration particularly in overcoming deficiencies associated with the latter mode of administration. Problems such as high first pass metabolism and drug degradation in gastrointestinal environment can be avoided by administering the drug via the buccal route. Moreover, buccal drug absorption can be promptly terminated in case of toxicity by removing the dosage form from the buccal cavity. It is also possible to administer drugs to patients who cannot be dosed orally to prevent accidental swallowing.

Advantages of Buccal drug delivery system^[12]

- Ease of administration.
- Termination of therapy is easy.
- Permits localization of the drug to the oral cavity for a long period of time.
- Can be administered to unconscious patients.
- Excellent route for the systemic delivery of drugs with high first pass metabolism and offers a greater bioavailability.
- Provides significant reduction of dose and its side effects.
- Drugs with poor bioavailability can be administered conveniently.
- Offers a passive system for drug absorption and does not require any activation.

Disadvantages of Buccal drug delivery system^[14]

- Drugs that irritate oral mucosa cannot be administered.
- Drugs that are unstable at buccal pH cannot be administered.
- Food and liquid consumption may not be convenient.
- Accidental swallowing of formulation by patients is possible.
- Excess salivation may cause swallowing of drug.

Basic components of Buccal drug delivery system^[15]

1. Drug substance
2. Bioadhesive polymer.
3. Backing membrane.
4. Permeation enhancers.

Buccal mucoadhesive tablets^[16]

Buccal mucoadhesive tablets are dry dosage forms that have to be moistened prior to placing in contact with buccal mucosa. Most commonly investigated dosage form tablets are small, flat and oval with a diameter of approximately 5-8 mm. They may be prepared by using different methods like wet granulation technique or direct compression technique.

DRUG PROFILE^[17]**Chemical Structure**

Fig. 03: Structure of Zaleplon.

Generic name: Zaleplon

IUPAC name: *N*-[3-(3-cyanopyrazolo[1,5-*a*] pyrimidin-7-yl) phenyl]-*N*-ethylacetamide

Molecular weight: 305.341 g/mol **Molecular formula:** C₁₇H₁₅N₅O **Melting point:** 180 – 187 °C **Category:** Sedative and Hypnotic **Bioavailability:** 30% **Elimination half-life:** 1 hour **Pka:** 7.71

Water Solubility: 0.0403 mg/mL

Dose: 5 to 20 mg

Description: white to off-white powder

Pharmacology

Zaleplon is a high selectivity and high affinity ligand of positive modulatory benzodiazepine sites on GABA_A receptors. Zaleplon binds preferentially at benzodiazepine sites on α1-

containing GABAA receptors which largely mediate the sedative effects of benzodiazepines. However, zaleplon binds with appreciable affinity to benzodiazepine sites on some $\alpha 2$ and $\alpha 3$ containing GABAA receptors which are implicated in the anxiolytic and muscle relaxant effects of benzodiazepines. Zaleplon is an ultrashort-acting sedative-hypnotic drug used to treat insomnia. Zaleplon increases EEG power density in the δ -frequency band and a decrease in the energy of the θ -frequency band.

Pharmacodynamic

Zaleplon is a nonbenzodiazepine hypnotic from the pyrazolopyrimidine class and is indicated for the short-term treatment of insomnia. Zaleplon also binds selectively to the CNS GABAA- receptor chloride ionophore complex at benzodiazepine (BZ) omega-1 (BZ1, $\omega 1$) receptors. The onset of action of Zaleplon is about 15 to 30 minutes with effect lasting between 4 to 6 hrs.

Mechanism of action

Zaleplon exerts its action through subunit modulation of the GABABZ receptor chloride channel macromolecular complex. Zaleplon also binds selectively to the brain omega-1 receptor located on the alpha subunit of the GABA-A/chloride ion channel receptor complex and potentiates t-butyl-bicyclophosphorothionate (TBPS) binding.

Pharmacokinetics

Absorption: Zaleplon is rapidly and almost completely absorbed following oral administration. Peak plasma concentrations are attained within 1 h after oral administration. Although zaleplon is well absorbed its absolute bioavailability is approximately 30% because it undergoes significant presystemic metabolism.

Distribution: The volume of distribution of zaleplon has been determined to be 1.27 L/kg or 90 L for a 70 kg person. This large volume of distribution indicates extensive distribution to extravascular tissue which is not uncommon for lipophilic compounds such as zaleplon.

Metabolism: Zaleplon is primarily metabolized by aldehyde oxidase.

Elimination: Zaleplon is metabolized primarily by the liver and undergoes significant presystemic metabolism. After oral administration zaleplon is extensively metabolized with less than 1% of the dose excreted unchanged in urine. Renal excretion of unchanged zaleplon

accounts for less than 1% of the administered dose.

Adverse effects

Dizziness, drowsiness, tingling and weakness.

Therapeutic uses

Zaleplon is used on a short-term basis to treat insomnia (difficulty in falling asleep).

Storage: Tight and light resistant container at 20-25 °C.

INSOMNIA^[18]

Insomnia is a common clinical problem and most common among sleep disorders. It is relatively common in females, old age persons and persons of lower socio-economic status. It is also a common symptom among psychiatric patients with 50-80% of population facing difficulty either in falling or staying asleep. Nearly 25% of the adults are affected by insomnia and 10% are chronic. Sleeplessness is categorized as irregular waking, early morning awakening, low sleep quality and sleep difficulties.

The treatment of insomnia comprises both pharmacologic and behavioral approaches. In many instances improvement of sleep hygiene may relieve problems initiating sleep. Cognitive behavioral therapy can be helpful to improve sleep hygiene. The various sedative and hypnotic drugs include Temazepam, Diazepam, Estazolam, Triazolam and other medicines. The various Non-benzodiazepine Hypnotic drugs include Zolpidem, Zaleplon and Eszopiclone.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

List of Material

Table No. 01: List of materials used.

Sl. No	Materials	Source
01	Zaleplon	Centaur Pharmaceuticals Pvt. Ltd. Mumbai
02	β – Cyclodextrin	HiMedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. Maharashtra, India.
03	Sodium CMC	Ozone International Pvt. Ltd. Mumbai
04	Crospovidone	Yarrow chem products. Mumbai, Maharashtra.
05	Microcrystalline Cellulose	Yarrow chem products. Mumbai, Maharashtra.
06	Magnesium Stearate	S.D. fine-chem limited, Mumbai, India.
07	Talc	Nice Chemicals Pvt. Ltd. Kerala, India
08	Mannitol	Loba Chemie Pvt. Ltd. Mumbai, India.

List of Equipment's

Table No. 02: List of equipment's used.

Sl. No	Equipment's Used	Source
01	UV Visible Spectrophotometer	UV – 1800, Shimadzu corporation, Japan.
02	Hardness tester	Pfizer hardness tester.
03	Thickness apparatus	Vernier caliper.
04	Friability apparatus	Lab India analytical.
05	Tablet compression machine	Rotary tablet punching machine
06	Dissolution test apparatus	TDT 08L, Electro lab, Mumbai, India
07	FTIR	Bruker alpha, Germany.
08	Differential Scanning Colorimetry	DSC-60, Shimadzu corporation, Japan.
09	Stability chamber	Analytical technologies.

METHODS

Preformulation studies

a. Solubility studies of pure drug in different solvents and media^[19]

Solubility studies for Zaleplon were performed by using various solvents like Water, Ethanol, DMSO, Chloroform and different media like phosphate buffer pH 6.8 and 0.1N Hcl. Unknown amount of pure drug was placed in 10 ml volumetric flask and with known amount of different Media and Solvents. The volumetric flasks were placed on rotary shaker for 48 hrs at 100 rpm. At the end of the studies, the solutions were filtered through Whatman filter paper, suitably diluted and finally analyzed using UV-visible spectrophotometer (UV 1800, Shimadzu, Japan) using suitable blank at 232 nm.

b. Melting point^[20]

The melting point of Zaleplon was determined by Capillary tube method using Thiel's tube instrument in which sample was inserted into a capillary tube having one end sealed and then this filled capillary tube was inserted in the Thiel's tube which was filled with Liquid paraffin up to a certain level. Then this tube was heated in controlled manner with the help of the burner. The temperature at which drug sample starts to melt was noted as melting point temperature and the temperature was noted.

c. Determination of λ_{\max} of Zaleplon^[21]

100 mg of Zaleplon was weighed accurately and transferred in 100 ml volumetric flask. Initially it was dissolved in 10 ml ethanol and makeup the volume with Phosphate buffer pH 6.8. The final solution contained 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Zaleplon as a stock solution A. The resultant solution is scanned in the range of 200-400nm by UV spectrophotometer (UV-1800 Shimadzu corporation, Japan) to get absorption maximum (λ_{\max}) and peak was noted.

Calibration curve of Zaleplon in Phosphate buffer pH 6.8

100 mg of Zaleplon drug was accurately weighed and transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flask, initially the drug was dissolved in 10 ml ethanol and adjusted the volume up to 100 ml with Phosphate buffer pH 6.8 to get stock solution A. From the stock solution A, 10 ml was pipetted out into another 100 ml volumetric flask and volume was made up to the mark with Phosphate buffer pH 6.8 to get stock solution B. From the stock solution B, known volume of aliquots 0.2ml, 0.4ml, 0.6ml, 0.8ml and 1ml were pipetted out and made up to 10 ml with Phosphate buffer pH 6.8 to get the solution containing 2 μ g/ml, 4 μ g/ml, 6 μ g/ml, 8 μ g/ml and 10 μ g/ml as the final solutions. Then, these final solutions were measured in a UV visible spectrophotometer (UV 1800, Shimadzu, Japan) at 232 nm for the absorbance. The absorbance of each was measured at 232 nm using Phosphate buffer pH 6.8 as a blank. The standard graph was plotted with concentration on x-axis and absorbance on y-axis the method validated for linearity, accuracy and precision. The method obeys Beer-Lamberts law in the concentration range of 2-10 μ g/ml.

Drug-Excipient Compatibility Study

a. FT-IR Study

FT-IR spectra of pure drug, excipients and physical mixture was analyzed using FT-IR Spectrophotometer (BRUKER ALPHA E). The samples were placed in sample holder and scanned in the spectral region between 4000 cm^{-1} to 600 cm^{-1} and the data was collected.

b. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)^[22]

Thermal analysis of pure drug and physical mixture and formulation was analyzed using DSC-60 calorimeter (Shimadzu, Japan). The Samples of drug and physical mixture was taken in an aluminum pan, sealed with aluminum cap and kept under nitrogen purging (atmosphere) with a flow rate of 50ml/min. The samples were scanned from 0-300 $^{\circ}$ C with the heating rate of 10 $^{\circ}$ C rate/min using differential scanning calorimeter.

Preparation of solid dispersion of Zaleplon by Kneading method^[23]

Solid dispersion was prepared to improve solubility of drug and mask the bitter taste of drug Hence, β - Cyclodextrin was used as the polymer. The kneading method was used for the preparation of solid dispersion of Zaleplon. Drug and β - Cyclodextrin were taken in ratios of 1:0.5, 1:1, 1:1.5 and 1:2. Polymer was wetted in a glass mortar with ethanol- water 50% (v/v) solution until a paste was obtained (about 30% of the total weight of polymer and Zaleplon).

The required amount of Zaleplon was then slowly added and the slurry was kneaded for about 45 min. Further, the product was dried under vacuum for 24 hrs and stored in a desiccator.

Solubility analysis of prepared solid dispersion^[24]

The solubility studies of prepared solid dispersions were performed in distilled water and phosphate buffer pH 6.8. An unknown amount of solid dispersion was taken and transferred into the conical flask which contain 10 ml of phosphate buffer pH 6.8, thereafter the samples were placed on a Rotary shaker and agitated at room temperature for 48 hrs. Finally, the solutions were filtered through Whatman filter paper, suitably diluted and analyzed spectrophotometrically at 232 nm.

Percentage Drug Content of prepared solid dispersion^[56]

Inclusion complexes equivalent to 100 mg of Zaleplon was precisely weighed and dissolved in 100 ml of Phosphate Buffer pH 6.8 solution. The solution was filtered through filter paper and suitably diluted. The solution was analyzed in UV Visible spectrophotometer at 232 nm and drug content was calculated by given formula.

$$\% \text{ Drug Content} = \frac{\text{Actual weight of drug in solid dispersion}}{\text{Theoretical weight of drug in solid dispersion}} \times 100$$

Pre compression study^[25]

a. Bulk density

Precisely weighed all amount of powder was passed through sieve #60 and transferred in measuring cylinder. Value measured by volume occupied by powder without any tapping on cylinder so the formula given below.

$$\text{Bulk Density} = \frac{\text{Weight of blend or powder}}{\text{Tapped volume of blend or powder (ml)}}$$

b. Tapped Density

Accurately weighed amount of powder was transferred into measuring cylinder and fixed it on tapping apparatus. Reading was taken after tapped it up to 100 cycles and calculated by using formula shown below.

$$\text{Tapped Density} = \frac{\text{Weight of blend or powder}}{\text{Tapped volume of blend or powder (ml)}}$$

c. Compressibility Index

Is a measure of the propensity of a powder to be compressed. It is determined from the bulk

and tapped densities and is calculated using the following formula.

$$\text{Carr's index} = \frac{(\text{Tapped density} - \text{Bulk density})}{\text{Tapped density}} \times 100$$

d. Hausner's ratio

Hausner's ratio is an indirect index of ease of powder flow. It is calculated by the following formula.

$$\text{Hausner's ratio} = \frac{\text{Tapped density}}{\text{Bulk density}}$$

e. Angle of repose

To measure the angle of repose, a funnel was fixed to a stand so that the lower tip of the funnel is 2.5 cm above the surface. A graph paper was placed on a flat surface. The powder blend was allowed to fall freely on the graph paper through the funnel, till the tip of the heap formed just touches the funnel. The radius of the heap was noted and from this angle of repose was determined. Angle of repose less than 30° suggests free flowing properties of the material.

$$\tan \theta = \frac{h}{r}$$

Where,

θ is the angle of repose

h is the height of the cone r is radius of the cone base.

Preparation of Buccal tablet by direct compression method^[26]

Buccal tablets of Zaleplon were prepared by a direct compression method. Before going to direct compression drug- β cyclodextrin inclusion complex, Sodium CMC and Crospovidone were thoroughly blended in a glass mortar with a pestle for 15 minutes then, MCC and Mannitol were added and blended for 2 more minutes. Blended mixture was screened through sieve no #60. After sufficient mixing magnesium stearate and talc were added and again mixed for additional 2-3 minutes. The mixture is compressed using an 8 mm punch on a rotary tablet punching machine.

Experimental Design

Response surface methodology (RSM) based on a central composite design was used to optimize the compositions of Zaleplon buccal tablets. The effects of two independent variables i.e., Sodium CMC (X1) and Crospovidone (X2) on two response variables,

Mucoadhesive strength (Y1) and % drug release (Y2) were studied. RSM design along with coded and uncoded levels is presented in Table No. 05 Central composite design (CCD) and quadratic model was used to design this experiment. Thirteen treatments, including four axial points, four factorial points and five central points were randomly performed according to CCD, which is summarized in Table No. 06.

Table No. 03: Independent variables and their corresponding levels.

Independent variables	Symbol	Coded levels				
		- α	-1	0	+1	+ α
Sodium CMC (mg)	X1	1.171	2	4	6	6.828
Crospovidone (mg)	X2	5.171	6	8	10	10.828

Table No. 04: Formula used for the formulation of Zaleplon buccal tablets as per the runs given by the central composite design.

Sl No	Ingredients (mg)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12	F13
01	Factor X1: Sodium CMC (mg)	4	6.83	4	2	4	4	4	4	4	6	1.17	2	6
02	Factor X2: Crospovidone (mg)	8	8	8	10	8	8	10.83	5.17	8	6	8	6	10
03	Zaleplon: Beta cyclodextrin complex equal to 5mg dose	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16
04	Microcrystalline Cellulose	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
05	Magnesium stearate	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
06	Talc	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
07	Mannitol	103	100.2	103	103	103	103	100.2	105.83	103	103	105.83	107	99
Total		200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200

Optimized formulation

The optimized Zaleplon buccal tablet formula was obtained by using Design Expert® software by applying constraints on Mucoadhesive strength (minimum) and % drug release (maximize). The suggested optimized Zaleplon buccal tablet formula was then prepared and evaluated to check validity of the calculated optimal formulation factors and predicted responses given by the software.

Table No. 05: The suggested optimized Zaleplon buccal tablets.

Sl No	Ingredients	OPT – F (mg)
01	Factor X1: Sodium CMC	4.1079
02	Factor X2: Crospovidone	9.92798
03	Zaleplon: β - cyclodextrin (Complex)	16
04	Microcrystalline Cellulose	65

05	Magnesium Stearate	2
06	Talc	2
07	Mannitol	100.96
Total		200

Statistical Analysis

Experimental datas were statistically analyzed using Design Expert® software (Version 13, Stat-Ease Inc., MN, USA). Numerous statistical parameters (lack-of-fit, predicted and adjusted multiple correlation coefficients and coefficient of variation) of different polynomial models were compared to select the best fitting polynomial model. Significant difference was determined through analysis of variance by calculating F value at the probability of 0.5, 0.1 and 0.01. To understand the effect of Sodium CMC and Crospovidone on response variables, response plots were generated using Design Expert® software (Version 13, Stat-Ease Inc., MN, USA). Finally, the validation of the models was assessed by performing the experiments at the optimal factor levels and the experimental values were compared with the predicted ones.

EVALUATION OF PREPARED BUCCAL TABLETS POST COMPRESSION STUDIES

a. Uniformity of weight^[27]

20 tablets were randomly selected from each batch and individually weighed using an electronic balance. The average weight was calculated and percent variation of each tablet was calculated.

b. Hardness test^[28]

The hardness of Six randomly selected tablets from each batch was measured using Monsanto hardness tester by placing each tablet diagonally between the two plungers and applying pressure until the tablet broke down into two parts completely and expressed in Kg/cm². The mean and standard deviation values were calculated and reported.

c. Thickness test^[29]

Six randomly selected tablets from each formulation were used for thickness determination. Thickness of each tablet was measured in mm using a digital Vernier Caliper. The average values were calculated.

d. Friability test^[30]

This was determined by weighing 20 tablets and placing them in the friabilator and rotating

the plastic cylinder vertically at 25 rpm for 4 min. After dusting the remaining weight of the tablets were recorded and % friability was calculated by using following formula.

$$\% \text{ Friability} = \frac{\text{Weight}(\text{final}) - \text{Weight}(\text{initial})}{\text{Weight}(\text{initial})} \times 100$$

e. Drug content uniformity^[31]

5 tablets were crushed in mortar and powder equivalent to 5 mg of Zaleplon was taken. The powder was dissolved in 100 ml of phosphate buffer pH 6.8. The solution was kept in rotary shaker for 24 h. The contents were analyzed by using UV spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-1601) at 232 nm. The study was performed in triplicate and results were represented as mean \pm SD (n=3).

f. Swelling index^[32]

The degree of swelling of bioadhesive polymers is an important factor affecting adhesive strength. A tablet was weighed and placed in a petridish containing 5 ml of phosphate buffer pH 6.8. Tablets were taken out at specified interval from the petridish and excess water was removed carefully by using filter paper. Then swelling Index was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Swelling index (SI)} = \frac{W_t - W_o}{W_o} \times 100$$

Where,

W_t = Weight of tablets after time t .

W_o = Weight of tablet before placing in the petridish.

g. Mucoadhesive Strength^[33]

It is used to measure the adhesive force of the buccal tablet with an Adhesive plate. Plates were cut with the area of 1 cm sq. The polymer was prewetted with water/buffer and placed on the surface of the plate. Tablet was kept in contact with the plate under the force of fingertip for 2 min before the measurement. The peak force required to detach the polymer from the plate was measured.

h. *In-vitro* Dissolution studies^[34]

Dissolution testing was carried out with "Paddle type II USP dissolution test apparatus" at rpm 50 and temperature $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ both dissolution media (Phosphate buffer pH 6.8) and water. Buccal tablet was made to stick on bottom of the Paddle (so as to allow one sided release from the tablet). At each specified intervals of time 5 ml samples were taken at 0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25

and 30 minutes and replaced with equal amount of fresh media. The samples were analytically tested to determine the concentration by UV spectroscopy method at wavelength of 232 nm. The % drug release was calculated using an equation obtained from the calibration curve.

Drug Release Kinetics Study^[71,72,73]

Zero-order model^[35]

Drug dissolution from dosage forms that do not disaggregate and release the drug slowly can be represented by the equation.

$$C_0 - C_t = K_0t$$

Rearrangement of equation

$$C_t = C_0 - K_0t$$

Where,

C_t = Amount of drug released at time t .

C_0 = Initial concentration of drug at time ($t=0$). K_0 = Zero order rate constant.

Thus, zero order kinetics defines the process of constant drug release from a drug delivery system and drug level in the blood remains constant throughout the delivery. Hence, to study the drug release kinetics data obtained from In-vitro dissolution study is plotted against time i.e., cumulative drug release versus time. Hence the slope of the above plot gives the zero-order rate constant and the correlation coefficient of the above plot will give the information about whether the drug release follows zero order kinetics or not.

First order kinetic model

This model is used to describe the absorption and elimination of some drugs, although it is difficult to understand the mechanism on the theoretical basis. It can be defined as that the first order process is the one whose rate is directly proportional to the concentration of the drug undergoing reaction i.e., greater the concentration faster the reaction. Hence, it follows linear kinetics. The drug release which follows the first order kinetic can be expressed by the equation.

$$\log C = \log C_0 - K_1t/2.303$$

Where,

K_1 = First order rate constant expressed in time⁻¹ or per hour. C_0 = Initial concentration of

the drug.

C = Percent of drug remaining at time t. t = Time.

Hence, to study the drug release kinetics data obtained from In-vitro dissolution study is plotted against time i.e., log % drug remaining versus time which yield a straight line with slope = $-K/2.303$ of the plot gives the first order rate constant. The correlation coefficient of the above plot will give the information about whether the drug release follows first order kinetics or not.

Higuchi model

Higuchi published the probably most famous and most often used mathematical equation to describe drug release from matrix system. This model is often applicable to the different geometrics and porous system. In the release environment perfect sink conditions are maintained. The basic equation of Higuchi model is:

$$C = [D (2qt - C_s) C_s t]^{1/2}$$

Where,

C = Total amount of drug release per unit area of the matrix (mg/cm^2).

D = Diffusion coefficient for the drug in the matrix (cm^2/hr).

Qt = Total amount of drug in a unit volume of matrix (mg/cm^3).

Cs = Dimensional solubility of drug in the polymer matrix (mg/cm^3). t = Time (hr).

The data obtained were plotted as cumulative percentage of drug release verses square root of time.

Korsmeyer-Peppas model

Korsmeyer and Peppas derived a simple relationship which described the drug release from a polymeric system. To illustrate the mechanism of drug release, first 60% of drug release data was fitted in Korsmeyer-Peppas model.

$$M_t/M_\infty = K_{kp} t^n$$

Where,

M_t/M_∞ = Fraction of drug released at time t.

M_t = Amount of drug released in time t.

M_∞ = Amount of drug released after time ∞ .

N = Diffusional exponent or drug release exponent. K_{kp} = Korsmeyer release rate constant.

To study release kinetics a graph is plotted between log cumulative % drug release log (M_t/M_∞) versus log time ($\log t$).

Stability Studies^[36]

Stability can be defined as the capacity of drug product to remain within specifications established to ensure its identity, strength, quality and purity. Stability study was done according to ICH guidelines to assess the combined effect of drug and excipients on the stability of the formulation. Optimized formulation was packed in aluminum foil in tightly closed container and stored at $30\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ 65% RH or $40\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ / 75% RH. The samples were evaluated for the Weight variation, Hardness, Drug content, Mucoadhesive strength and *In-vitro* drug release study after 90 days.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preformulation studies

a. Solubility studies of Zaleplon in different solvents and media Table No. 06: Solubility studies of Zaleplon in different solvents

Drug	Solubility in Distilled water mg/ml	Solubility in Ethanol mg/ml	Solubility in DMSO mg/ml	Solubility in Chloroform mg/ml
Zaleplon	0.034	32.82	27.60	1.54

Table No. 07: Solubility studies of Meclizine hydrochloride in different media.

Drug	Solubility in PBS 6.8 mg/ml	Solubility in 0.1N Hcl mg/ml
Zaleplon	1.427	0.342

b. Melting point Determination

The values discussed in the literature is $180 - 187^\circ\text{C}$. This close alignment with the expected range indicates the purity and stability. The melting point of Zaleplon is done by Thiel's tube instrument and the melting point was found to be **185°C** .

Calibration curve of Zaleplon

Table No. 08: Calibration curve Zaleplon in Phosphate buffer pH 6.8.

Sl. No.	Con ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance at 232 nm	
		X	RSD (%)
01	0	0	0
02	2	0.150	0.0098
03	4	0.296	0.0044
04	6	0.446	0.0029
05	8	0.589	0.0023
06	10	0.726	0.0018

Fig. 04: Calibration Curve of Zaleplon in Phosphate buffer pH 6.8.

The calibration curve of Zaleplon was developed in the range of 2 - 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ at wavelength of 232nm. The standard calibration curve obeys Beer-Lambert's law, gives linear curve and R^2 values is 0.9998.

Drug-Excipients Compatibility Studies FTIR

Fig. 05: FTIR spectra of Pure Drug.

Fig 06: FTIR spectra of Physical mixture.

Table No. 09: Interpretation of IR.

Formulation Code	CH (cm ⁻¹)	C≡N (cm ⁻¹)	C=O (cm ⁻¹)	C=C (cm ⁻¹)	C=N (cm ⁻¹)	OH (cm ⁻¹)
Zaleplon	2977	2227	1645	1543	1481	-
Physical mixture	2915	2231	1645	1575	1451	3325

The IR spectra of pure drug showed peak at **2977 cm⁻¹** is due to presence of **C-H** group stretching. **2227 cm⁻¹** is due to presence of **C≡N** stretching. **1645 cm⁻¹** is due to presence of **C=O** stretching. **3303 cm⁻¹** is due to presence of **OH** stretching. All these similar peaks were present in OPT -F also. It indicates that there was no much deviation in the peaks. This shows there was no drug and excipients interaction and it shows that excipients were compatible with the drug.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry

Fig. 08: DSC thermogram of OPT - F.

The DSC thermogram of Zaleplon showed an endothermic peak at **181.36 °C** and the prepared OPT – F of buccal tablets showed endothermic peak at **176.65 °C**. There was no appreciable change in the melting point of prepared Zaleplon Buccal Tablets compared to that of pure drug.

Solubility studies of prepared solid dispersion

Table No. 10: Solubility studies of prepared solid dispersion.

Media	Solid dispersion	Solubility (mg/ml)
Water	1:0.5	0.265 ±0.0014
	1:1	0.835 ±0.0021
	1:1.5	1.349 ±0.0007
	1:2	2.163 ±0.0014
Phosphate buffer pH 6.8	1:0.5	1.518 ±0.007
	1:1	1.971 ±0.0049
	1:1.5	2.581 ±0.0007
	1:2	2.997 ±0.002

The data shows substantial influence of β - cyclodextrin on the solubility of the prepared complexes. The solubility will increase with increase in the amount of β - cyclodextrin up to the optimum level. Among these complexes, 1:2 showed highest solubility compared to pure drug and other solid dispersion.

Drug content of solid dispersion

Table No. 11: Comparison of drug content of prepared Zaleplon Solid dispersion.

Drug - carrier Ratio	Percentage of Drug content
1:0.5	83.77±0.014
1:1	86.55±0.021
1:1.5	90.24±0.010
1:2	93.08±0.018

Pre compression study

Table No. 12: Precompression studies of powder blend.

Batch	Bulk density	Tapped density	Hausner's ratio	Carr's index	Angle of repose
F1	0.43±0.001	0.46±0.0017	1.07±0.0022	6.69±0.19	25.53±0.46
F2	0.42±0.0015	0.47±0.0025	1.12±0.0024	10.65±0.19	21.96±0.13
F3	0.41±0.0020	0.44±0.0030	1.08±0.0021	6.98±0.18	23.63±0.11
F4	0.47±0.0021	0.50±0.0020	1.10±0.0013	6.23±0.11	22.55±0.48
F5	0.48±0.0025	0.51±0.0026	1.12±0.0012	5.72±0.10	24.16±0.29
F6	0.40±0.0030	0.43±0.0015	1.08±0.0043	7.19±0.37	22.26±0.23
F7	0.45±0.0025	0.49±0.0025	1.09±0.0014	8.35±0.12	20.4±0.35
F8	0.45±0.0015	0.48±0.0026	1.06±0.0023	5.94±0.20	24.06±0.11
F9	0.41±0.0021	0.45±0.0025	1.11±0.0011	8.75±0.09	21.46±0.45
F10	0.46±0.0031	0.49±0.0035	1.13±0.0020	5.87±0.18	25.16±0.15

F11	0.42±0.0038	0.46±0.0021	1.09±0.0049	8.59±0.41	26.23±0.40
F12	0.49±0.0040	0.52±0.0031	1.11±0.0025	5.53±0.22	23.23±0.25
F13	0.40±0.0042	0.44±0.0035	1.10±0.0082	8.58±0.48	21.26±0.46
OPT - F	0.44±0.0021	0.47±0.0020	1.09±0.0014	6.2±0.12	24.23±0.23

Formulated buccal tablets

Fig. 09: Directly compressed Buccal tablets.

Experimental Design

Table No. 13: Experimental runs projected, observed and predicted responses.

Runs	Formulation Code	Factor 1 X1: Sodium CMC (mg)	Factor 2 X2: Crospovidone (mg)	Response 1 Y1: Mucoadhesive Strength (gram)		Response 2 Y2: Drug release (%)	
				Observed value	Predicted value	Observed value	Predicted Value
01	F 1	4	8	13.90	14.00	92.10	92.01
02	F 2	6.828	8	17.89	17.90	89.30	89.31
03	F 3	4	8	14.10	14.00	92.00	92.01
04	F 4	2	10	10.80	10.75	95.20	95.30
05	F 5	4	8	14.00	14.00	92.07	92.01
06	F 6	4	8	13.90	14.00	92.10	92.01
07	F 7	4	10.828	12.90	13.12	93.90	93.96
08	F 8	4	5.171	14.20	14.23	90.00	90.07
09	F 9	4	8	14.10	14.00	92.00	92.01
10	F 10	6	6	16.90	16.89	88.70	88.73
11	F 11	1.171	8	9.96	10.01	94.80	94.71
12	F 12	2	6	11.50	11.46	92.50	92.55
13	F 13	6	10	16.50	16.48	91.50	91.48

The levels of the studied factors were chosen so that their feasibility and relative differences were suitable to have a quantifiable effect on the response.

ANOVA- Analysis of variance

Table No. 14: ANOVA analysis of RSM quadratic model for Mucoadhesive strength (Y1) Response.

Source	Coefficient estimation	Sum of square	F - value	p - value	
Model	14	63.57	494.11	< 0.0001	Significant
X1 – Sodium CMC	2.79	62.24	2418.88	< 0.0001	
X2 - Crospovidone	-0.3673	1.08	41.94	0.0003	
X1X2	0.0750	0.0225	0.8744	0.3809	
X1 ²	0.0094	0.0006	0.0238	0.8818	
X2 ²	-0.1781	0.1801	8.58	0.0221	
Residual		0.1801			
Lack of fit		0.1401	4.67	0.0853	Not Significant

Table No. 15: ANOVA analysis of RSM quadratic model for % drug release (Y2) Response.

Source	Coefficient estimation	Sum of square	F - value	p - value	
Model	92.05	44.37	2920. 21	< 0.0001	Significant
X1 – Sodium CMC	-1.91	29.18	9601.39	< 0.0001	
X2 - Crospovidone	1.38	15.17	4991.08	< 0.0001	
X1X2	0.0250	0.0025	0.8227	0.3946	
X1 ²	-0.0082	0.0005	0.1558	0.7048	
X2 ²	-0.0582	0.0236	7.77	0.0270	
Residual		0.0213			
Lack of fit		0.0110	1.42	0.3617	Not Significant

After experimentally obtaining Responses Y1 and Y2 an analysis of variance (ANOVA) is performed. The actual (experimental) values are then compared with the predicted values to assess the model's accuracy. p-values (degree of significance) less than 0.05 indicate model terms are significant. F-value for the Lack of Fit of Y1 and Y2 responses are **4.67** and **1.42** respectively, which implies the Lack of Fit is not significant i.e., our model is statistically accurate.

Model Summary Statistics

Table No. 16: Model Summary Statistics: Influence of formulation variables on the response factors.

Response factors	Std. Dev	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Predicted R ²	Adequate Precision
Y1	0.1604	0.9972	0.9952	0.9834	72.3941
Y2	0.0551	0.9995	0.9992	0.9975	175.5201

It can be observed that R² (**0.9972 and 0.9995**) is high for both responses which indicates a high degree of correlation between the experimental and predicted responses. The Predicted R² value of Y1 and Y2 are **0.9834 and 0.9975** respectively and the adjusted R² value of Y1 and Y2 are **0.9952 and 0.9992** respectively. In addition, the predicted R² value is in good agreement with the adjusted R² value because the difference between predicted and adjusted R² value is less than 0.2 which resulting in reliable models. Adequate precision of Y1 and Y2 are **72.3941 and 175.5201** respectively i.e., greater than 4, which indicate an adequate signal. Hence this model can be used to navigate the design space.

Verification of Model Adequacy

Fig. 10: Distribution of actual (experimental) vs predicted values of the regression model of mucoadhesive strength. (Y1).

Fig 11: Distribution of actual (experimental) vs predicted values of the regression model of % drug release. (Y2).

It can be observed that the predicted values came closer to the actual ones and all points on the scatter plot followed a straight line. This implied that the quadratic regression model fitted realistically, thereby adequately expressing the experimental range studied.

Response Surface Analysis

Fig. 12: Contour plot [A] and 3D response surface plot [B] showing the influence of two factors on Mucoadhesive strength (Y1)

Fig. 13: Contour plot [A] and 3D response surface plot [B] showing the influence of two factors on Cumulative %drug release in 30 min (Y2).

Post compression studies of Buccal tablets

Table No. 17: Post compression studies of Buccal tablets formulation. (Weight variation, Thickness, Hardness and Friability).

Formulation Code	Weight variation (mg)	Thickness (mm)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability (%)
F1	199.05±1.10	3.12±0.0089	4.83±0.14	0.839±0.06
F2	201.35±1.84	3.13±0.0075	4.85±0.10	0.699±0.03
F3	196.8±1.32	3.12±0.0051	4.45±0.18	0.701±0.04
F4	204.15±1.53	3.18±0.0082	4.98±0.23	0.336±0.02
F5	199.8±1.85	3.16±0.0055	4.66±0.12	0.483±0.02
F6	201.05±1.67	3.12±0.0080	4.96±0.25	0.857±0.05
F7	198.8±1.88	3.14±0.0052	4.72±0.31	0.71±0.02
F8	203.8±1.61	3.13±0.0075	5±0.41	0.718±0.07
F9	197.75±1.99	3.12±0.0063	4.47±0.12	0.49±0.07
F10	202.1±2.31	3.18±0.0082	4.76±0.26	0.726±0.06
F11	200.95±1.28	3.13±0.0041	4.52±0.12	0.697±0.03
F12	198.1±2.02	3.15±0.0040	4.68±0.17	0.485±0.02
F13	200.8±1.82	3.14±0.0063	4.5±0.14	0.478±0.04
OPT-F	200.75±1.33	3.14±0.0098	4.71±0.11	0.611±0.02

The weight variation test of all formulation showed minimal weight variation with a mean of **196.8±1.32 to 204.15±1.53 mg** respectively and OPT-F was found to be **200.75±1.33 mg**. The thickness of all formulation was found to be **3.12±0.0051 to 3.18±0.0052 mm** and OPT-F was found to be **3.14±0.0098 mm**. The hardness of all formulation was found to be **4.45±0.18 to 5±0.41 kg/cm²** and OPT-F was found to be **4.71±0.11 kg/cm²**. The friability of the buccal tablet was used to determine the mechanical strength of the buccal tablets. The percentage

friability of all formulation was found to be **0.336±0.02 to 0.857±0.05** respectively and OPT-F was found to be **0.611±0.02%** was less than 1% indicating good mechanical resistance. The above post compressional evaluation was within the limit

Table No. 18: Post compression studies of Buccal tablet formulation. (Drug content, Swelling index and Mucoadhesive strength).

Formulation Code	Drug content (%)	Swelling index (%)	Mucoadhesive strength (gram)
F1	97.849±0.46	47.92±0.58	13.90±0.95
F2	91.228±0.36	55.01±0.56	17.89±0.65
F3	95.789±0.29	48.75±0.78	14.1±0.92
F4	98.645±0.25	43.49±0.76	11.1±0.78
F5	96.042±0.19	48.53±0.73	14±0.77
F6	97.326±0.17	47.77±0.57	13.90±0.69
F7	95.789±0.50	46.28±0.49	12.90±0.82
F8	93.573±0.42	48.92±0.58	14.2±0.66
F9	94.300±0.22	48.74±0.73	14.1±0.92
F10	91.228±0.54	53.40±0.63	16.9±0.93
F11	98.378±0.36	40.15±0.71	9.7±0.90
F12	96.551±0.46	44.14±0.47	11.5±0.43
F13	95.288±0.40	52.76±0.76	16.5±0.65
OPT-F	95.789±0.33	47.53±0.70	13.62±0.66

The drug content of the prepared buccal tablet was found between **91.228±0.54 to 98.645±0.25** % respectively and OPT-F was found to be **95.789±0.33** %.

The residence time of any formulation in the Oral cavity is affected by the swelling index of polymers. As the excess swelling of the tablets causes the rapid clearance of the formulation from oral cavity and may cause the difficulty in drug release. Swelling index of all formulation was found to be **40.15±0.71 to 55.01±0.56** % respectively and OPT-F was found to be **47.53±0.70** %.

Mucoadhesive Strength of all Zaleplon Buccal Tablets was found to be in the range of **9.7±0.90 to 17.89±0.65 gram**. It was found that increasing the amount of Sodium CMC resulted in the increase in the mucoadhesive strength but drug release was found to be decreased. Vice versa increasing the amount of Crospovidone resulted in increase in the drug release but mucoadhesive strength was found to be decreased. The selected optimized (OPT-F) buccal tablets balances both mucoadhesive strength and % drug release by ensuring immediate release while maintaining acceptable mucoadhesive strength (**13.62**) gram.

***In-vitro* Dissolution Studies of Zaleplon Buccal Tablets**

Fig. 14: Graph of *In-vitro* drug release of Pure drug and Zaleplon Buccal Tablets from F1 to F7.

Fig. 15: Graph of *In-vitro* drug release of Pure drug and Zaleplon Buccal Tablets from F8 to F13 and OPT-F.

The percentage of drug dissolution for pure drug Zaleplon shows **23.32 % within 30 mins**. The percentage of drug dissolution from formulations **F1 to F13** ranges from **88.7±0.29 to 95.21±0.33 % within 30 mins** and for the optimized formulation **OPT-F** suggested by Design-Expert® software showed **93.15±0.38 % of drug dissolution within 30 mins**.

Different Drug Release Kinetics models

Fig. 16: Graph of First order kinetics for *In-vitro* drug release of Buccal Tablets formulation from F1 to F13 and OPT-F.

Fig 17: Graph of Peppas model for *In-vitro* drug release of Buccal Tablets formulation from F1 to F13 and OPT-F.

Fig. 18: Graph of Higuchi model for *In-vitro* drug release of Buccal Tablets formulation from F1 to F13 and OPT-F.

Table No. 19: Regression co-efficient (R^2) values and ‘n’ values of Buccal tablets formulation from F1 to F13 and OPT-F according to different kinetic models.

Formulation code	Zero order		First order		Higuchi	Peppas	
	R^2	n	R^2	n	R^2	R^2	n
F1	0.8779	2.8805	0.9929	0.084	0.9857	0.9695	0.5080
F2	0.8990	2.8224	0.9913	0.073	0.9859	0.9715	0.5554
F3	0.8818	2.8781	0.9928	0.083	0.9863	0.9704	0.5144
F4	0.8636	2.9411	0.9918	0.100	0.9847	0.9683	0.4736
F5	0.8799	2.8796	0.9929	0.084	0.9860	0.9700	0.5112
F6	0.8779	2.8805	0.9929	0.084	0.9857	0.9695	0.5080
F7	0.8727	2.9095	0.9910	0.091	0.9858	0.9694	0.4927
F8	0.8939	2.8644	0.9923	0.077	0.9846	0.9700	0.5573
F9	0.8818	2.8781	0.9928	0.083	0.9863	0.9704	0.5144
F10	0.9027	2.7898	0.9888	0.071	0.9864	0.9732	0.5633
F11	0.8628	2.9127	0.9874	0.095	0.9833	0.9638	0.4733
F12	0.8779	2.8899	0.9931	0.086	0.9860	0.9699	0.5062
F13	0.8909	2.8970	0.9918	0.081	0.9844	0.9688	0.5509
OPT-F	0.8762	2.8831	0.9895	0.086	0.9863	0.9702	0.5005

Here highest degree of correlation coefficient values of the release data of all formulation seems to fit better with **first order** as the evident Here Zaleplon buccal tablets formulation release kinetics is fitted in korsmeyer-peppas equation. ‘n’ values were in between **0.47 to 0.56** so the release is the following **non-Fickian kinetics**.

Short-term Stability Studies

Table No. 20: Physicochemical evaluation of OPT Zaleplon Buccal Tablets after stability studies. ($40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$).

Sl. No.	Parameters	Before stability testing	After stability testing
01	Weight Uniformity (mg)	200.75 \pm 1.33	200.12 \pm 1.22
02	Hardness (Kg/cm ²)	4.6 \pm 0.11	4.54 \pm 0.09
03	Drug Content Uniformity (%)	95.78 \pm 0.33	95.23 \pm 0.31
04	Mucoadhesive strength (gram)	12.96 \pm 0.66	12.42 \pm 0.64
05	<i>In-vitro</i> Dissolution study (%)	93.15 \pm 0.38	92.98 \pm 0.32

There was no significant difference in the physicochemical parameters and *In-vitro* drug release with the initial results. This indicates that the prepared OPT-F was found to be stable.

CONCLUSION

In this study, the Zaleplon Buccal tablets are prepared by direct compression method by employing Response Surface Methodology (RSM) based on Central Composite Design (CCD). This study concludes that the production of Zaleplon buccal tablet was feasible and

demonstrated rapid release of drug i.e. fast onset of action. To offer patients a more convenient method of administration, we have developed a Zaleplon buccal tablets, which is currently unavailable in the market. Zaleplon buccal tablets were dissolved in saliva without need of water and absorbed through buccal mucosa which shows fast onset of action. Overall work suggests that the optimized Zaleplon buccal tablets formulations (OPT-F) as recommended by Design Expert® software (central composite design) was found to show the best results by ensuring acceptable mucoadhesive strength and immediate release for fast onset of action.

REFERENCES

1. Jain NK. Controlled and novel drug delivery. 1st ed. New Delhi. CBS Publishers & Distributors, 1997; 3(2): 52-81.
2. Rossi S, Sandri G, Caramella CM. Buccal drug delivery: a challenge already won. Drug DIS Today, 2005; 2(1): 59-65.
3. Vyas SP, Khar RK. Controlled drug delivery-concepts and advances. 1st ed. New Delhi: Vallabh Prakashan, 2002; 1(5): 411-417.
4. Harris D, Robinson JR. Drug delivery via the mucous membranes of the oral cavity. J of pharm sci., 1992; 81(1): 1-10.
5. P Chinna R, KSC C, Y Madhusudan R. < A> review on bioadhesive buccal drug delivery systems: current status of formulation and evaluation methods, 2011; 19(6): 385-403.
6. Yadav VK, Gupta AB, Kumar R, Yadav JS, Kumar B. Mucoadhesive polymers: means of improving the mucoadhesive properties of drug delivery system. J. Chem. Pharm. Res., 2010; 2(5): 418-32.
7. Rao NR, Shravani B, Reddy MS. Overview on buccal drug delivery systems. J of pharm sci and res., 2013; 5(4): 80.
8. Ahuja A, Khar RK, Ali J. Mucoadhesive drug delivery systems. Drug Deve and Indus pharm., 1997; 23(5): 489-515.
9. Rana S, Gupta PK, Swain SR. Buccal Drug Delivery System: A Comprehensive Review. Inter J of Pharm Sci and Medi., 2024; 9(6): 104-118.
10. Chaudhari VA, Sarode SM, Sathe BS, Vadnere GP. Mucoadhesive Buccal Drug Delivery System: A Review. Pharm Sci Moni., 2014; 5(2): 142-162.
11. Yamsani V, Gannu R, Kolli C, Rao M, Yamsani M. Development and evaluation of buccoadhesive carvedilol tablets. Acta Pharm., 2007; 57(2): 185-97.
12. Shinkar DM, Dhake AS, Setty CM. Drug delivery from the oral cavity: A focus on mucoadhesive. PDA J. Pharm. Sci. Technol., 2012; 66: 466-500.

13. Gawas SM, Dev A, Deshmukh G, Rathod S. Current approaches in buccal drug delivery system. *Pharm Biol Eval.*, 2016; 3(2): 165-77.
14. Mozammel F, Dewan I, Islam SA. A Comprehensive Review on Buccal Drug Delivery System. *World J of Pharm and Pharm Sci.*, 2019; 8(12): 77-93.
15. <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Zaleplon>.
16. Bheemsain T, Kar SK. An overview of insomnia management. *Delp Psychiatry J.*, 2012; 15(2): 294-301.
17. Abdelbary GA, Amin MM, Abdelmoteleb M. Novel mixed hydrotropic solubilization of Zaleplon: Formulation of oral tablets and in-vivo neuropharmacological characterization by monitoring plasma GABA level. *J of Drug Deli Sci and Tech.*, 2016; 33: 98-113.
18. Noman MA, Alburyhi MM, Alqubati MA. Preformulation and characterization studies of Clopidogrel active ingredient for Oro dispersible tablets development. *World J Pharm Pharm Sci.*, 2024; 13(3): 996-1015.
19. Waghmare A, Pore Y, Kuchekar B. Development and characterization of zaleplon solid dispersion systems: a technical note. *A aps Pharm sci tech.*, 2008; 9(1): 536-43.
20. Chinta DP, Katakam P, Murthy VS, Newton MJ. Formulation and in-vitro evaluation of moxifloxacin loaded crosslinked chitosan films for the treatment of periodontitis. *J of pharm res.*, 2013; 7(6): 483-90.
21. Darwish MK. Preparation and Evaluation of Zaleplon Fast Dissolving Films Using Different Film Forming Agents, 2014; 5(4): 2055-2060.
22. Kumar BP, Kavitha P, Devi KJ. Formulation design and evaluation of mucoadhesive buccal tablets of nitroglycerin. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci.*, 2014; 6(7): 251-9.
23. Tikait AV, Wankhade VP, Mhaske Y, Atram SC, Bobade NN, SD P. Formulation and Evaluation Immediate Release Mucoadhesive Buccal Tablet of Midodrine HCL. *Asian J of Pharm Res and Devel*, 2024; 12(4): 28-36.
24. Popescu C, Manda P, Juluri A, Janga KY, Cidda M, Murthy SN. Enhanced dissolution efficiency of zaleplon solid dispersions via modified β -cyclodextrin molecular inclusion complexes. *J of Pharm and Pharm Sci.*, 2015; 1(1): 1-0.
25. *Indian pharmacopeia*, 2007; 1: 241.
26. Martin A. Micromeritics In: *Physical Pharmacy*, 6th Edn (editors: Baltimore MD) Lippincott Williams and Wilkins, 2001; 423-454.
27. Rajiv G. Pre-formulation: A need for dosage form design. *Pharm info. Net*, 2008; 6(2): 25-31.
28. Lachman L, Lieberman HA, Kanig JL. *The theory and practice of industrial pharmacy*.

- Philadelphia: Lea & Febiger, 1976; 5(1): 210-212.
29. evaluation of controlled release mucoadhesive buccal tablets of Candesartan. *J of Pharm and Cosme*, 2011; 1(2): 125-30.
30. Alexander A, Ajazuddin GT, Sawrna SP. Various evaluation parameters used for the evaluation of different mucoadhesive dosage forms: a review. *Int J Drug Formul Res.*, 2011; 2(3): 893-903.
31. Azim MS, Mitra M, Bhasin PS, Alam MM, Husain A. Development of Dissolution Medium for Candesartan Cilexetil by RP-HPLC Method. *Am. J. Pharm Tech Res.*, 2012; 2(3): 892-903.
32. Reddy PD, Balanjineyulu R, Swarnalatha D, Badarinath AV, Gopinath C. Design, development and in vitro characterization of felodipine mucoadhesive buccal tablets. *J. Pharm. Res.*, 2015; 9(2): 170-6.
33. Ashok T, Gudas GK, Bingi M, Subaldebnath KC, Bhattacharjee C. Design and evaluation of controlled release mucoadhesive buccal tablets of Candesartan. *J of Pharm and Cosme*, 2011; 1(2): 125-30.
34. Alexander A, Ajazuddin GT, Sawrna SP. Various evaluation parameters used for the evaluation of different mucoadhesive dosage forms: a review. *Int J Drug Formul Res.*, 2011; 2(3): 893-903.
35. Dash S, Murthy PN, Nath L, Chowdhury P. Kinetic modeling on drug release from controlled drug delivery systems. *Acta Polonia Pharm.*, 2010; 67(3): 217-23.
36. Azim MS, Mitra M, Bhasin PS, Alam MM, Husain A. Development of Dissolution Medium for Candesartan Cilexetil by RP-HPLC Method. *Am. J. Pharm Tech Res.*, 2012; 2(3): 892-903.